

Customer Service, Customer's Satisfaction and Customer's Loyalty of Selected Casual Dining Restaurants in Santa Rosa Laguna

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ABSTRACT

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This study examined the relationship among customer service, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna. Using a descriptive- correlational design, data were collected from 340 customers selected through simple random sampling across five restaurants. A validated, researcher-made questionnaire measured five dimensions of customer service reliability, responsiveness, assurance, tangibles, and empathy alongside levels of satisfaction and loyalty. Results showed that overall customer service was rated "Strongly Agree" ($M = 3.25$), with tangibles ranking highest ($M = 3.30$), followed by responsiveness ($M = 3.28$), assurance ($M = 3.26$), empathy ($M = 3.25$), and reliability ($M = 3.18$). Customer satisfaction and loyalty were both rated "Very High" ($M = 3.28$ and $M = 3.27$, respectively). Pearson r correlation analysis indicated significant relationships: service dimensions correlated moderately with satisfaction ($r = .416$ to $.584$, $p < .01$) and loyalty ($r = .258$ to $.415$, $p < .01$), while satisfaction and loyalty also showed a moderate positive correlation ($r = .486$, $p < .01$). Findings confirm that improved customer service enhances satisfaction, which in turn strengthens loyalty. The study recommends action plans focused on staff training, loyalty programs, and customer engagement to sustain service quality and promote long-term business growth.

KEYWORDS:

Customer Service, Customer Satisfaction, Customer Loyalty, Casual Dining Restaurants, SERVQUAL, Correlational Study

INTRODUCTION

Casual dining restaurants occupy a vital niche in the food service industry, combining the efficiency of fast-casual establishments with the comfort of full-service dining. They typically provide table service, varied menus, a family-friendly atmosphere, and moderate pricing, catering to a wide demographic seeking convenience, quality, and comfort (Johnson, 2022). With the growth of the hospitality sector in urban areas such as Santa Rosa, Laguna, the casual dining segment has expanded alongside rising consumer expectations.

Customer service is a critical factor in retention and business sustainability. Anania (2024) defines it as continuous assistance from initial contact to post-purchase interactions,

encompassing empathy, reliability, and attentiveness that foster long-term relationships. Gupta (2024) similarly highlights consistency, personalization, and prompt issue resolution as defining superior service that enhances satisfaction and loyalty.

Customer satisfaction, defined as how well an organization meets or exceeds expectations, is a key indicator of business success (Patel, 2020). Satisfied customers often become advocates, generating repeat patronage and positive word-of-mouth. Customer loyalty, described as an enduring emotional commitment that drives repeat purchases and fosters brand trust (George et al., 2022), further enhances profitability and competitive advantage (Ranabahat, 2019).

Despite extensive global research on satisfaction and loyalty, limited studies focus on casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa. This study examines the relationship between customer service, satisfaction, and loyalty in selected establishments. Guided by SERVQUAL Theory, Disconfirmation Theory, and Perceived Risk Theory, it explores how reliability, responsiveness, assurance, tangibles, and empathy affect satisfaction and loyalty. Findings aim to inform strategies to enhance service delivery

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and strengthen customer relationships in the casual dining sector.

METHODS

This study employed a descriptive–correlational design to examine the relationships among customer service, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna. Descriptive research characterized customers' perceptions of service quality, satisfaction, and loyalty, while correlational analysis measured the degree of association among variables using Pearson *r* (Copeland, 2022).

The population comprised customers from five selected restaurants, each serving approximately 450 customers daily, totaling an estimated 2,250 guests. Using the Raosoft calculator at a 95% confidence level and 5% margin of error, the required sample size was 340 respondents. Simple random sampling ensured each customer had an equal chance of selection. Respondents were approached during or after dining, informed of the study's purpose, and assured of voluntary participation, confidentiality, and anonymity. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately to ensure data accuracy.

The main instrument was a researcher-made

questionnaire with three sections measuring customer service (reliability, responsiveness, assurance, tangibles, and empathy), customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty. Content and face validation were conducted by a research adviser, statistician, and hospitality management expert. Cronbach's Alpha confirmed strong internal consistency across all constructs. Data collection was conducted with permission from restaurant management and the Graduate School Dean. The researcher personally administered the questionnaires, providing instructions before respondents completed them. Weighted mean was used to determine levels of customer service, satisfaction, and loyalty, while Pearson *r* tested the significance of relationships among variables at 0.01 and 0.05 significance levels to ensure accuracy and reliability of findings.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings of the study on customer service, customer satisfaction, and customer loyalty in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna. The results are organized according to the study's research questions and hypotheses, supported by statistical data, relevant literature, and interpretation.

1. Customer Service in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in The City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Table 1 The Customer Service in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa Laguna: Reliability

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The casual dining restaurant provides the service they promised.	3.34	Strongly Agree	1
2. The casual dining restaurant is dependability in handling customers' service problems.	3.25	Strongly Agree	2
3. The employees in casual dining restaurant performs service right the first time.	3.08	Agree	8
4. The employees in casual dining restaurant provides services as the promise time.	3.21	Agree	3.5
5. The casual dining restaurant maintains error-free environment.	3.12	Agree	6
6. The employees in casual dining restaurant are dependable and consistent.	3.21	Agree	3.5
7. The employees in casual dining restaurant address mistakes right away.	3.15	Agree	5
8. The employees in casual dining restaurant serve exactly as ordered.	3.09	Agree	7
Average Weighted Mean	3.18	Agree	

As shown in Table 1, customer service in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna, regarding reliability, was interpreted as agree, with an average weighted mean of 3.18, indicating that customers generally perceive the restaurants as reliable.

The indicator "The restaurant provides the service they promised" ranked first, reflecting strong recognition of

commitment fulfillment, followed by "The restaurant is dependable in handling service problems" in second place. "Employees provide services at the promised time" and "Employees are dependable and consistent" tied for third, highlighting timeliness and consistency. "Employees address mistakes right away" ranked fifth, "Restaurants maintain an error-free environment" sixth, "Employees serve exactly as

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ordered” seventh, and “Employees perform the service right the first time” ranked eighth.

These findings support Adiele (2020), who noted that consistent and reliable service builds customer trust, enhances satisfaction, and encourages repeat patronage. Career Guide

(2024) similarly emphasizes that reliability strengthens service quality, enables efficient problem resolution, and fosters customer confidence, ultimately contributing to organizational growth and competitiveness.

Table 2. The Customer Service in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa Laguna: Responsiveness

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The casual dining restaurants employees provide prompt service.	3.18	Agree	8
2. The employees of casual dining restaurant give extra efforts to handle customers request.	3.39	Strongly Agree	1
3. All casual dining restaurants employees are informing every guest when services will be performed.	3.29	Strongly Agree	4
4. All casual dining restaurants employees are always willing to help customers.	3.31	Strongly Agree	2
5. All employees of casual dining restaurants are maintaining the speed and quality service during busy time.	3.29	Strongly Agree	3
6. All casual dining restaurants employees are knowledgeable on handling different guest complaint.	3.23	Agree	7
7. All employees of casual dining restaurant are never too busy in responding customer’s request.	3.26	Strongly Agree	6
8. The casual dining restaurants employees will not keep the guest waiting.	3.28	Strongly Agree	5
Average Weighted Mean	3.28	Strongly Agree	

As shown in Table 2, customer service in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna, regarding responsiveness, was interpreted as strongly agree, with an average weighted mean of 3.28, indicating that customers perceive the restaurants as highly responsive to their needs.

The indicator “Employees give extra effort to handle customers’ requests” ranked first, highlighting the value placed on initiative and attentiveness. “Employees are always willing to help customers” ranked second, followed by “Employees maintain speed and quality service during busy hours” in third, and “Employees inform guests when services will be performed” in fourth. “Employees will not keep

guests waiting” ranked fifth, “Employees are never too busy to respond” sixth, “Employees are knowledgeable in handling guest complaints” seventh, and “Employees provide prompt service” eighth.

These findings support Fontanella (2023), who emphasized that responsiveness significantly impacts dining experience, loyalty, and reputation. Nambisan et al. (2019) similarly noted that minimizing waiting time and promptly addressing requests enhances perceived service quality. Attentive and timely service fosters customer satisfaction and encourages repeat patronage.

Table 3. The Customer Service in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in The City of Santa Rosa, Laguna: Assurance

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The employees in casual dining restaurant can be able to answer questions completely.	3.23	Agree	5.5
2. The employees in casual dining restaurant are able and willing to give information.	3.38	Strongly Agree	1
3. All employees are well trained, competent, and experienced.	3.32	Strongly Agree	2

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4. The employees in casual dining restaurant makes me feel personally safe.	3.28	Strongly Agree	3
5. Employees of casual dining restaurant are supported to do their job well.	3.26	Strongly Agree	4
6. Employees of casual dining restaurant are consistently courteous.	3.20	Agree	7
7. Employees of casual dining restaurants instill confidence to the customers.	3.23	Agree	5.5
8. The employees of casual dining restaurants are always polite.	3.17	Agree	8
Average Weighted Mean	3.26	Strongly Agree	

As shown in Table 3, customer service in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna, regarding assurance, was interpreted as strongly agree, with an average weighted mean of 3.26, indicating that customers generally feel confident and secure in the staff’s competence and professionalism.

The indicator “Employees are able and willing to give information” ranked first, highlighting the importance of communication and transparency. “Employees are well-trained, competent, and experienced” ranked second, followed by “Employees make me feel personally safe” third, and “Employees are supported to do their job well” fourth.

“Employees can answer questions completely” and “Employees instill confidence in customers” tied for fifth, while “Employees are consistently courteous” ranked seventh, and “Employees are always polite” eighth.

These findings align with Klaus (2022), who emphasized that assurance builds trust, manages expectations, and enhances the dining experience. Well-trained and knowledgeable staff foster customer loyalty and strengthen competitive advantage. Similarly, Wu et al. (2019) noted that employee skills inspire trust and make customers feel valued and safe, increasing the likelihood of repeat patronage and a positive brand reputation.

Table 4. The Customer Service in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa Laguna: Tangible

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The casual dining restaurant has attractive parking area and building exteriors.	3.34	Strongly Agree	2
2. The casual dining restaurant has visually attractive dining area.	3.32	Strongly Agree	4.5
3. The employees of casual dining restaurants are always neat and appropriately dressed.	3.33	Strongly Agree	3
4. The menu in casual dining restaurant is easily readable.	3.37	Strongly Agree	1
5. The dining area is always clean.	3.32	Strongly Agree	4.5
6. The casual dining restaurant has comfortable seats in dining area.	3.26	Strongly Agree	6
7. The dining area is comfortable and easy to move around.	3.25	Strongly Agree	7
8. Restrooms are always clean and fresh.	3.19	Agree	8
Average Weighted Mean	3.30	Strongly Agree	

As shown in Table 4, customer service in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna, regarding tangibles, was interpreted as strongly agree, with an average weighted mean of 3.30, indicating that customers perceive the physical facilities, appearance, and overall environment as highly satisfactory and appealing.

The indicator “The menu is easily readable” ranked

first, highlighting the positive impact of clear menu design. “Attractive parking areas and building exteriors” ranked second, followed by “Employees are neat and appropriately dressed” third. “Visually attractive dining area” and “Dining area is always clean” tied for fourth, “Comfortable seating” ranked sixth, “Dining area is easy to move around” seventh, and “Restrooms are always clean and fresh” ranked eighth.

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These findings align with Zygiaris et al. (2022), who emphasized that tangible elements such as cleanliness, ambiance, and aesthetics significantly shape customer perceptions and overall dining experience. Ryu and Jang (2019) similarly noted that ambient factors, including music,

aroma, temperature, and employee appearance, influence emotional responses and post-dining behavior. Prioritizing physical comfort and visual appeal enhances satisfaction, strengthens brand image, and encourages repeat visits.

Table 5. The Customer Service in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa Laguna: Empathy

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The casual dining restaurant employees give customers individual attention.	3.28	Strongly Agree	2
2. All casual dining restaurants employees understand the needs of the customers.	3.27	Strongly Agree	4
3. The employees of casual dining restaurants are sympathetic and reassuring if something is wrong.	3.28	Strongly Agree	2
4. The employees are always sensitive to the needs and wants of every customers.	3.25	Strongly Agree	6
5. The casual dining restaurants operates convenient business hours.	3.26	Strongly Agree	5
6. The casual dining restaurant have customer’s interest at heart.	3.20	Agree	7.5
7. The casual dining restaurant employees understand the specific needs of the customers.	3.28	Strongly Agree	2
8. The casual dining restaurants employee always understand the customers.	3.20	Agree	7.5
Average Weighted Mean	3.25	Strongly Agree	

As shown in Table 5, customer service in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna, regarding empathy, was interpreted as strongly agree, with an average weighted mean of 3.25, indicating that customers perceive employees as attentive, understanding, and responsive to individual needs.

The indicators “Employees give customers individual attention,” “Employees are sympathetic and reassuring if something is wrong,” and “Employees understand the specific needs of customers” tied for second, emphasizing personalized and considerate service. “Employees understand customers’ needs” ranked fourth, “Restaurant operates convenient business hours” fifth,

“Employees are sensitive to customer needs and wants” sixth, and “Restaurant has customers’ best interests at heart” and “Employees always understand customers” tied for seventh.

These findings support Beth (2022), who highlighted that empathy is critical for creating meaningful dining experiences, enhancing satisfaction, loyalty, and positive word-of-mouth. By adopting the customer’s perspective, recognizing preferences and concerns, and responding appropriately, staff foster long-term patronage. Murray et al. (2019) similarly noted that empathy involves courtesy, friendliness, individualized attention, and clear communication, helping customers feel valued and understood.

Table 6. Summary Table of the Customer Service in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa Laguna

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Reliability	3.18	Agree	5
2. Responsiveness	3.28	Strongly Agree	2
3. Assurance	3.26	Strongly Agree	3
4. Tangibles	3.30	Strongly Agree	1
5. Empathy	3.25	Strongly Agree	4
Overall Weighted Mean	3.25	Strongly Agree	

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As shown in Table 6, the overall level of customer service in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna, was interpreted as strongly agree, with an overall weighted mean of 3.25, indicating that customers perceive services as reliable, responsive, assuring, tangible, and empathetic.

Among the service dimensions, tangibles ranked highest (3.30), reflecting the importance of physical

facilities, cleanliness, and ambiance. Responsiveness followed (3.28), highlighting prompt and attentive service. Assurance ranked third (3.26), emphasizing staff competence and professionalism, while empathy placed fourth (3.25), indicating that personalized attention contributes to satisfaction. Reliability ranked fifth (3.18), showing that consistent and dependable service remains essential, though slightly lower in perceived impact.

2. The Level of Customers’ Satisfaction in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in The City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Table 7. The Level of Customers’ Satisfaction in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa Laguna

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. The products sold are of the highest quality.	3.16	High (Agree)	8
2. The staffs are approachable and treat the customer with patience and respect.	3.35	Very High (Strongly Agree)	2
3. The casual dining restaurants meets my needs and expectation	3.28	Very High (Strongly Agree)	4.5
4. Satisfied with the products and services offered by the casual dining restaurants	3.37	Very High (Strongly Agree)	1
5. Satisfied with the casual dining restaurants staff response and prompt services.	3.33	Very High (Strongly Agree)	3
6. It is more likely to recommend the casual dining restaurants to other people.	3.28	Very High (Strongly Agree)	4.5
7. Have a good and positive impression of the casual dining restaurants	3.25	Very High (Strongly Agree)	7
8. It would visit the casual dining restaurants again.	3.26	Very High (Strongly Agree)	6
Average Weighted Mean	3.28	Very High (Strongly Agree)	

As shown in Table 7, the level of customer satisfaction in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna, was interpreted as very high, with an average weighted mean of 3.28, indicating that customers are generally satisfied with products and services and perceive staff as courteous, patient, and respectful.

The indicator “I feel satisfied with the products and services offered” ranked first (3.37), showing that overall satisfaction is strongly influenced by product and service quality. “The staff are approachable and treat customers with patience and respect” ranked second (3.35), followed by “I am satisfied with staff response and prompt service” third (3.33). “The restaurants meet my needs and expectations” and

“I am likely to recommend the restaurants to others” tied for fourth (3.28). “I would visit the restaurants again” ranked sixth (3.26), followed by “I have a good and positive impression of the restaurants” seventh, and “The products sold are of the highest quality” eighth.

These findings align with Kim et al. (2022), who emphasized that customer satisfaction is critical for the success and sustainability of casual dining establishments. Piccoli et al. (2019) similarly noted that satisfaction fosters loyalty, repeat patronage, and positive word-of-mouth, directly contributing to long-term retention and sustainable growth.

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3. The Level of Customers’ Loyalty in Selected Casual Dining in The City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Table 8 The Level of Customers’ Loyalty in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa Laguna

Indicator	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Majority of casual dining restaurant visit are from this store.	3.26	(Very High) Strongly Agree	4
2. Continue to favor the promotions of this casual dining restaurants instead of others.	3.21	(High) Agree	8
3. Intend to keep buying the products from this casual dining restaurant.	3.36	(Very High) Strongly Agree	1
4. Recommend the casual dining restaurants to others	3.25	(Very High) Strongly Agree	5.5
5. Continue to visit the casual dining restaurants even if its product’s prices increased.	3.30	(Very High) Strongly Agree	2
6. A loyal patron of this casual dining restaurants.	3.22	(High) Agree	7
7. The products from this casual dining restaurants is the best choice.	3.25	(Very High) Strongly Agree	5.5
8. Intend to do more visits to this restaurant in the coming weeks.	3.28	(Very High) Strongly Agree	3
Average Weighted Mean	3.27	(Very High) Strongly Agree	

As shown in Table 8, the level of customer loyalty in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna, was interpreted as very high, with an average weighted mean of 3.27, indicating that customers consistently purchase products and visit these restaurants, even when prices increase, reflecting strong loyalty.

The indicator “I intend to keep buying products from this restaurant” ranked first (3.33), demonstrating commitment to repeat purchases. “I would continue visiting even if prices increased” ranked second (3.30), followed by “I intend to do more visits in the coming weeks” third (3.28), and “Majority of my visits are from this store” fourth (3.26). “I will recommend the restaurants to others” and “I love the

products because it is the best choice for me” tied for fifth (3.25). “I consider myself a loyal patron” ranked seventh (3.22), and “I continue to favor the restaurant’s promotions instead of others” ranked eighth (3.21).

These findings align with Kyurova et al. (2021), who emphasized that customer loyalty is essential for long-term success and growth in casual dining. Gallarza-Granizo et al. (2020) similarly noted that loyalty arises from delivering positive value, fostering repeat patronage, and generating favorable word-of-mouth. High-quality service and strong customer relationships support sustained business growth, brand resilience, and competitive advantage.

4. Relationship between the Customer Service and The Level of Customers’ Satisfaction in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in The City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Table 9. Relationship between the Customer Service and the Level of Customers’ Satisfaction in selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Customer Service	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
Reliability	0.269** Low correlation	0.000	Significant
Responsiveness	0.416** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
Assurance	0.464** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
Tangibles	0.481** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
Empathy	0.584** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

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As shown in Table 9, the relationship between customer service in terms of reliability and customer satisfaction yielded a Pearson r of 0.269, indicating a low positive correlation. The corresponding p-value of 0.000, below the 0.01 significance level, confirms statistical significance. Customer service dimensions of responsiveness, assurance, tangibles, and empathy showed moderate positive correlations with customer satisfaction, with Pearson r values of 0.416, 0.464, 0.418, and 0.584, respectively, all significant at the 0.01 level ($p = 0.000$).

These findings indicate that higher-quality customer service is associated with greater customer satisfaction in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna. This aligns with Zygiaris et al. (2022), who emphasized that service quality directly affects customer satisfaction, fostering loyalty, positive word-of-mouth, and long-term success. Risdah (2019) similarly noted that service quality good or poor determines satisfaction and can be assessed through instruments measuring various service dimensions.

5. Relationship between the Customer Service and The Level of Customers' Loyalty in Selected Casual Dining Restaurant in The City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Table 10. Relationship between the Customer Service and the Level of Customers' Loyalty in selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Customer Service	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
Reliability	0.316** Low correlation	0.000	Significant
Responsiveness	0.258** Low correlation	0.000	Significant
Assurance	0.308** Low correlation	0.000	Significant
Tangibles	0.361** Low correlation	0.000	Significant
Empathy	0.415** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

As shown in Table 10, the relationship between customer service dimensions reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and tangibles and customer loyalty revealed low positive correlations, with Pearson r values of 0.316, 0.258, 0.308, and 0.361, respectively. All p-values were 0.000, below the 0.01 significance level, indicating statistical significance. Empathy showed a moderate positive correlation with loyalty ($r = 0.415$, $p = 0.000$). These results indicate that there is a significant relationship between customer service and customer loyalty among selected casual dining restaurants in the City of Santa Rosa, Laguna. This implies that when restaurants demonstrate better quality customer service, customers are more likely to remain loyal and continue patronizing the establishment.

These results indicate that higher-quality customer service is significantly associated with greater customer loyalty in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna. This aligns with Dandotiya et al. (2020), who emphasized service quality as a key determinant of satisfaction and loyalty. Zhong and Moon (2020) similarly noted that service quality strongly influences satisfaction, essential for long-term success. Sharma (2020) highlighted that excellent service fosters loyalty by promoting positive experiences, building trust, resolving concerns efficiently, and creating emotional connections. Consistent high-quality service also generates positive word-of-mouth and provides valuable feedback to guide continuous improvement, further enhancing customer loyalty.

6. Relationship between the Level of Customers' Satisfaction and The Level of Customers' Loyalty in Selected Casual Dining in The City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

Table 11. Relationship between the Level of Customers' Satisfaction and the Level of Customers' Loyalty in selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa, Laguna

	Pearson r value	p-value	Interpretation
The Level of Customers' Satisfaction and the Level of Customers' Loyalty in selected Casual Dining Restaurant in the City of Santa Rosa, Laguna	0.486** Moderate correlation	0.000	Significant
**Significant @ 0.01			

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As shown in Table 11, the relationship between customer satisfaction and customer loyalty yielded a Pearson r of 0.486, indicating a moderate positive correlation. The p -value of 0.000, below the 0.01 significance level, confirms statistical significance. This suggests that higher customer satisfaction is associated with greater customer loyalty in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna.

These findings align with Ahlawat (2022), who emphasized that satisfied customers are more likely to return, recommend the restaurant, and maintain long-term patronage. By prioritizing satisfaction and delivering exceptional experiences, businesses can strengthen customer relationships and loyalty, leading to sustained success and profitability. Sani et al. (2022) similarly noted that satisfied customers often act as brand advocates, reinforcing loyalty and contributing to business growth and competitive advantage.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings, customer service in selected casual dining restaurants in Santa Rosa, Laguna demonstrates reliability in addressing customer concerns and understanding their needs. Customers are generally satisfied with the products and services, appreciating staff who treat them with patience and respect. Moreover, customers continue to purchase and revisit these restaurants even when prices rise, reflecting sustained loyalty. The study also shows that higher-quality customer service leads to increased customer satisfaction, which in turn promotes greater loyalty. Therefore, implementing an action plan to enhance customer service, sustain satisfaction, and strengthen loyalty is essential for improving the overall performance and competitiveness of casual dining establishments in Santa Rosa.

To improve service quality, area and store managers may conduct seminars and training programs to develop employees' skills in handling operations and engaging effectively with customers. These programs can help staff adapt to challenges, enhance interactions with customers and colleagues, boost morale, and cultivate a sense of urgency in addressing customer needs. Managers may also implement strategies to improve satisfaction through personalized services, targeted service improvements, and comprehensive staff development.

To foster customer loyalty, it is recommended to establish loyalty programs offering rewards, discounts, or exclusive promotions, while encouraging employees to communicate these benefits to guests. Emphasizing empathy in employee training can enhance service quality and promote a customer-centric culture. A systematic monitoring and evaluation process through surveys, feedback portals, or suggestion boxes should be implemented to continuously assess and improve service quality, satisfaction, and loyalty metrics. Managers are also encouraged to use these findings to refine strategies, strengthen customer relationships, and

ensure a continuous, systematic approach to service improvement. Finally, future research may further explore the relationships between customer service, satisfaction, and loyalty, including qualitative studies to validate these findings and enhance theoretical understanding in both local and international contexts.

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